

How to Achieve Sustainable Nuclear Education and Training – Examples of Success Stories from Chalmers University of Technology's Ecosystem

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ABSTRACT

Offering courses in nuclear engineering was challenging in some European countries during the last decade following the aftermaths of the Fukushima accident. With decreasing student enrollment, different initiatives were launched at Chalmers University of Technology, with the purpose of providing continued education and training in nuclear engineering, while being less vulnerable to variations in student interest. Thanks to the use of online and hybrid set-ups, different target audiences could be reached to guarantee a sufficient number of students. Several courses were created, each having different objectives in terms of course contents and corresponding target groups. The courses range from basic to advanced level, yet all courses attract enough participants to be sustainable in the long run. Beyond flexibility in attendance, state-of-the-art pedagogical methods relying on flipped classrooms were implemented. Those methods resulted in high student performance on the courses and high student satisfaction. This paper presents the entire ecosystem of courses developed at Chalmers University of Technology during recent years. Three courses are also chosen as illustrative examples of such efforts: one basic course open to all having an engineering background, one MSc course primarily offered to Chalmers students, but also to non-Chalmers students, professionals and PhD students, and finally a set of advanced MSc courses offered primarily to PhD and Post-Doc students and professionals, but also to MSc/BSc students, from all over the world. The ecosystem of courses developed is well adapted to be scaled up for meeting the current growing needs in education and training.

Keywords: Nuclear training and education, active learning, flipped classrooms, hybrid teaching/learning, online education

1. INTRODUCTION

The aftermaths of the Fukushima accident in 2011 had devastating effects on student enrollment at European universities in nuclear engineering. With phasing out programs shortly implemented in some countries after the accident and a rather uncertain future for the nuclear industry, student interest in nuclear-related subjects significantly dropped. This resulted in the closing of some nuclear engineering programs. Chalmers University of Technology was no exception, with its two-year master program in "Nuclear Science and Technology" offered last in the academic year 2017/2018.

Even if some basic courses in nuclear engineering were still offered as elective courses within other master programs, the possibility of offering more advanced courses completely disappeared. As MSc thesis projects typically capitalize on such advanced courses, this restricted the capability to recruit MSc students for those projects. Since MSc theses are often an entry point to subsequent PhD education, PhD positions had mostly external applicants, for whom it may be difficult to judge their suitability for PhD education.

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Based on some pilot courses offered on small scales in nuclear reactor modelling at Chalmers University of Technology [1- 4], a profound restructuring of the course offering was started. The incentives were manifold:

- To make the area more visible to students, both within and outside of Chalmers.
- To ensure the capability to offer advanced courses for few students, while educating a larger fraction at some more basic level.
- To mix students, both from Chalmers and outside, with professionals.
- To guarantee efficient student learning.

This paper describes the current course offering developed during recent years at Chalmers. After first providing an overview of the various courses, the educational principles on which the courses are based are explained. Finally, some of the courses are presented in more detail, with some brief analysis of the attractiveness of the courses and student performance on those.

2. OVERVIEW OF COURSE OFFERING

In the area of nuclear engineering and reactor physics/modelling in particular, different educational levels are targeted, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the course offering in nuclear engineering at Chalmers University of Technology.

To attract student to the area, a free self-paced fully online course titled “Introduction to nuclear engineering” is offered, accessible on two platforms: on [Chalmers webpage](#) directly using the Learning Management System (LMS) Canvas and on Learnify as three separate modules ([part 1](#), [part 2](#), and [part 3](#)) [5]. This course is open to all, both students (from Chalmers or from outside) and professionals. People registering for the course should nevertheless have some engineering background. The course details the underlying principles of nuclear reactors for the purpose of understanding the history of the development of nuclear power, and then focuses on how a nuclear reactor works, with emphasis on Light Water Reactor (LWR) technology. Finally, the aspects of nuclear power to be considered in a climate mitigation perspective, as well as the advantages/disadvantages of nuclear power, are presented.

For Chalmers students enrolled at the BSc level primarily, an interdisciplinary course titled “Modern energy technologies and systems” is given. This course can also be attended by MSc and PhD students and is also open to professionals. The course aims at presenting various energy technologies in a balanced way:

- Energy and transport systems

- Bioenergy and power-to-fuel
- Hydropower technology
- Wind power technology
- Solar power technology
- Nuclear power technology
- Batteries, fuel cells and electrolysis
- Environmental economics and energy policy

A team of teachers provide the course participants with an in-depth description of each technology, its advantage and disadvantage. This course is offered as part of the TRACKS initiative at Chalmers, which aims at tackling real-world problems through hands-on activities, while capitalizing on the variety of the background of the course participants [6]. This course also aims to advertise to Chalmers students the possibility to attend additional courses related to nuclear engineering at Chalmers, despite the absence of a master program on this specific subject.

At the MSc level, several guest lectures on nuclear power are arranged in various courses belonging to different master programs. Beyond a general introduction to nuclear science and technology, those lectures also advertise other more specialized courses that the students may want to attend later in their education. In a similar manner and as part of the course titled “Computational continuum physics” offered to the students enrolled in the Physics master program, numerical techniques used to solve large systems of linear and non-linear equations are presented, with hands-on activities on this subject all demonstrated on a sodium-cooled fast reactor. Those activities also aim at getting students interested in reactor physics and modelling.

For students who want to get further knowledge in the physics and safety of nuclear reactors, two TRACKS courses are given: a course titled “Nuclear reactor technology – Past, present and future” and a course titled “Nuclear power safety”. After introducing the history on nuclear power development, the first course focuses on the technology and physics of nuclear reactors. The course ends on discussing the advantages and disadvantages of nuclear reactors. After introducing some basic concepts in nuclear power safety, the second course tackles risk assessment and safety analysis. Both courses are also open to PhD students and professionals. The first course is also open to non-Chalmers students.

In the area of advanced level courses, Chalmers has been coordinating the Horizon 2020 [GRE@T-PIONEER](#) project, which aims at providing specialized education in computational and experimental nuclear reactor physics and safety [7]. The project, which ran between 2020 and 2024, has been recently converted into an Alliance, able to continue delivering the courses in the following subjects:

- Nuclear data for energy and non-energy applications
- Neutron transport at the fuel cell and assembly levels
- Core Modelling for core design
- Core modelling for transients
- Reactor transients, nuclear safety and uncertainty and sensitivity analysis
- Radiation protection in nuclear environment
- Hands-on on the AKR-2 training reactor
- Hands-on on the BME training reactor

The courses are offered by a team of 18 teachers from eight different universities throughout Europe, each teacher complementing each other with his/her respective expertise. As the courses are at an advanced level, the target audience is BSc/MSc students having already a solid background in reactor physics, PhD and Post-Doc students, as well as professionals. The courses are open to all.

The GRE@T-PIONEER courses are the results of the pilot course titled “Modelling of nuclear reactor multiphysics” first offered in 2019 and still regularly offered by Chalmers [4]. The principles established in this course were used as a basis to scale up the course offering by including other universities and teachers.

3. PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES

The pedagogy in all courses listed above is largely based on the concept of *active learning* [8]. This set-up offers ample time to the students to practice on well-designed activities, a principle often referred

to in every day's jargon as "learning by doing". It is demonstrated that active learning results in better fulfilment of course learning outcomes by the students.

Nevertheless, this pedagogical principle requires teacher support and guidance during such activities, as well as the acquisition of the necessary knowledge and concepts, before participating in the activities. To free up time in the classroom for concentrating on those activities, flipped classrooms are implemented in the courses [9-10]. In this format, the students need to study at their own pace some materials delivered to them ahead of the synchronous sessions typically through an LMS. Study time can thus be divided into two phases: an asynchronous learning phase, followed by a synchronous learning phase. Some examples of typical activities offered in the courses described in Section 2 are given in Figure 2. This figure categorizes the offered activities not only according to their asynchronous versus synchronous nature, but also to the necessary acquisition of knowledge/concepts versus their application. Examples of asynchronous activities focusing on acquisition are reading some handbooks, textbook or papers and watching some video lectures. Asynchronous activities targeting higher cognitive skills encompass online quizzes and participation in discussion fora. Examples of synchronous activities focusing on acquisition are lectures, whereas activities such as quizzes, discussions, and problem-solving target the upper end of the participation/acquisition axis. During the asynchronous learning phase, interactions between students and teachers are possible, but typically occur with some delay, due to the self-paced nature of the activities. On the other hand, the synchronous activities heavily rely on the simultaneous interactions between students and teachers. As the activities during such sessions are at a much more advanced level, it is the time when teacher support and guidance are required. Flipped classrooms aims at maximizing this time.

Figure 2. Overview of the various course elements offered in the courses, categorized along two dimensions following Hrastinski [11]: acquisition versus participation, and asynchronous versus synchronous..

In addition to the two dimensions listed above and illustrated in Figure 2, the courses presented in Section 2 are delivered in different formats:

- Fully online: the asynchronous and synchronous phases are both offered on the web.
- Hybrid: the asynchronous phase is delivered online, whereas the synchronous phase is delivered fully onsite or as a combination of both online and onsite.

Three examples of the above set-ups are described in the following section:

- The course "Introduction to nuclear engineering" as an example of fully onsite course.
- The courses "Nuclear reactor technology – Past, present and future" and the GRE@T-PIONEER courses as examples of hybrid courses.

4. SELECTED EXAMPLES OF SUCCESSFUL EDUCATIONAL INITIATIVES

4.1. Course “Introduction to nuclear engineering”

The course, which is a free self-paced online course, has been available on Learnify since 2023 and was launched on Chalmers platform at the end of October 2024. As no learning analytics data are available on Learnify, only the Chalmers version of the course is reported hereafter. Both versions of the course are very similar.

After enrolling on the course, the participants get access to a series of video lectures and slides intertwined with quizzes. Those resources are arranged in a specific order that the participants need to follow, i.e., it is not possible to bypass a resource. The quizzes aimed at testing the course participants' understanding of the topics covered in the videos and slides. Furthermore, successfully completing a quiz is required to get access to the subsequent teaching resource. An unlimited number of attempts on the quizzes is offered, so that the participants can train to get the right answer. A variety of quiz question types are used: true/false, multiple choice/answers, categorization, matching, ordering, hot spot. Also, a few more involved quizzes require the participants to use some formula, make some further derivations and answer some questions by providing numerical values. Not finding the right answer to those more difficult quizzes does not prevent accessing the following teaching resources. Automatic feedback is provided on all quizzes, both for correct and incorrect answers.

The participants can also put questions on a discussion forum. This forum is monitored by the teacher, who can intervene and help the course participants if need be.

The course represents ca. 40 hours of self-study work. After successfully completing all quizzes, the participants receive a certificate of successful completion of the course. The certificate mentions that the course is a self-paced course, the number of equivalent learning hours (40 hours), and the fact that completing the course and being issued a certificate is entirely based on watching the video lectures and correctly answering most of the quizzes (for which an unlimited number of attempts is allowed).

As of February 9th, 2026, the course had 581 people registered. 79 of those had obtained a course certificate. All participants need to answer a course evaluation before receiving their certificates. The participants' overall impression of the course was rated as 4.8 on the 1-5 Likert scale (with 1 corresponding to “very bad” and 5 to “very good”). When analyzing the feedback/comments from the students, the teaching quality and the course structure were highly praised. Students gained substantial knowledge. Some of the quizzes were nevertheless felt by some participants as challenging, especially the numerical ones. For those, some more examples (with step-by-step instructions) would have been beneficial, as well as some additional learning resources. Also, the course requires some basic knowledge in engineering mathematics, which may not be possessed by all. In all, the course was very well appreciated by diverse learners, from beginners to professionals, with or without prior knowledge in nuclear engineering.

4.2. Course “Nuclear reactor technology – Past, present and future”

The course was first launched in the academic year 2024/2025. The course is worth 7.5 European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ETCS) and represents 200 hours of work. The course spreads over a period of four months during the fall term.

The course is a flipped course with a study cycle of one week, i.e., the learning sequence represented in Figure 2 is repeated each week. This means that each week the students need to study some materials on their own (handbooks, short video lectures, and quizzes) to get prepared for a 4-hour long interactive session. Such sessions follow the principles of active learning, i.e., students work on small projects in groups under the guidance of the teacher.

Continuous assessment is used throughout the entire course, i.e., all activities undertaken during both the asynchronous and synchronous phases are graded. The asynchronous activities represent 25% of the final course score. To ensure that students do the preparatory work on time, those activities all have a deadline, after which they become unavailable to students (which would then result in a lower course score). The LMS also provides instantaneous information to the students about their current course score.

Some of the synchronous sessions are based on workshops involving several stakeholders from the Swedish nuclear industry. A workshop on safety culture is organized by the consultancy company Afry, and a workshop on the integration of nuclear in future energy systems is arranged by the utility Vattenfall. Laboratory exercises at the Jožef Stefan Institute TRIGA reactor in Ljubljana, Slovenia, are also given in a hybrid set-up, with 10 students from Chalmers following the exercises onsite in Slovenia and the remaining students following the exercises remotely.

During the first edition of the course, 42 students followed the whole course and obtained very high course scores, ranging from 81.1% to 98.6% of the maximum course score. In terms of course overall impression, 23 students answered the final course evaluation and rated the course as 4.2 on the 1-5 Likert scale (with 1 corresponding to “very poor” and 5 to “excellent”). When analyzing the feedback and comments from the students, the course organization and the teaching quality were highly appreciated. The synchronous sessions were nevertheless perceived in some cases as too much focused on deriving expressions and implementing, rather than understanding/reflecting on the learned concepts. In all, the course tackled different aspects of nuclear engineering, from the basic physical principles to discussing the advantages/disadvantages of nuclear technology and its potential benefits and shortcomings to mitigate the effects of global warming.

4.3. GRE@T-PIONEER courses

The GRE@T-PIONEER courses were first launched in the academic year 2022/2023 and re-offered in the academic year 2024/2025. All courses, except the hands-on sessions on the training reactors, are worth 3 ECTS and represent 80 hours of work.

Each course is given on five consecutive weeks following the learning sequence represented in Figure 2. The asynchronous learning phase (representing 40 hours of work) is available to students during the first four weeks and is taking place online for all. After completing a sufficient fraction of the asynchronous activities, the participants are then offered to participate in the synchronous activities representing 40 hours of work and organized during five consecutive days. The synchronous activities are organized in a hybrid set-up, with participants following the sessions either onsite or online. The asynchronous activities are based on reading sets of handbooks, watching short video lectures, taking some online quizzes and working on small computer-based assignments. The synchronous activities rely partly on quizzes/discussions, and mostly on more involved computer-based projects, carried out in groups.

All activities are graded, with the asynchronous ones representing 25% of the course final score. Participants obtaining at least 50% of the course final maximum score are then issued with a certificate of successful completion. The LMS also provides instantaneous information to the students about their current course score.

During the first two editions of the courses, 716 participants were enrolled in the LMS, out of which 504 qualified for participating to the synchronous sessions. Even if accepted to the synchronous sessions, not all participants show up at the sessions. 450 students actually participated in the synchronous sessions (either onsite or by taking the first activity for the remote attendees). Out of those, 411 students received a certificate of successful course completion, which represents a success rate of 91%. Looking at the two cohorts of participants, i.e., the ones participating in the sessions onsite, and the ones participating online, the success rates read as 100%, and 87%, respectively.

Across all courses throughout the first two editions of the courses, the course satisfaction ranged between 4.4 and 4.7 on a 1-5 Likert scale. In terms of student feedback and comments, the hands-on nature of the course, the quality of the course material and teaching, together with the course set-up and organization, were mentioned as the key positive aspects of the courses. Points to further improve were mostly related to the high pace of the courses and the corresponding workload. Despite offering the same learning environment to both the onsite and online students during the synchronous phase of the courses, collaboration between students was perceived as easier for the onsite students compared to the online students. On the other hand, the possibility of accessing the courses fully online made the courses available to participants who would never have had the opportunity to travel onsite.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The different educational initiatives presented above resulted in high student performance and satisfaction, demonstrating that the implemented pedagogical methods and set-up of the courses worked as intended. In addition to the efficacy of the teaching techniques relying on flipping, flexibility in attendance was provided by offering the courses fully online or in a hybrid format. This resulted in the possibility of reaching target audiences well beyond the usual borders of pure campus-based teaching. By mixing different target groups, a sustainable ecosystem of learning opportunities was created. Thanks to the volume of students the different courses attract, this ecosystem is much less sensitive to local variations in student interest and is thus much more robust to possible future and most likely inevitable fluctuations. Also, the collaboration between different teachers across several European countries has been instrumental in establishing a vivid educational network. The current course offering is also well adapted to be scaled up to meet the growing needs in education and training in nuclear engineering.

Further improvements to the courses are being investigated. Some additional support and resources would be beneficial for students having a background not necessarily in line with the required course prerequisites. Developing a Teaching Assistant chatbot is one way to be explored in different courses. Also, lowering the pace of the sessions to better secure student understanding is considered. Offering additional activities focusing on conceptual understanding rather than procedural understanding will be looked at. Finally, for hybrid set-ups involving onsite and online students, various group activities minimizing possible different learning experiences between those two cohorts will be implemented.

Discussions are ongoing at Chalmers University of Technology on the creation of larger master programs, in which specialization in different topics will be proposed. The incentive in the re-shaping of the master programs at Chalmers is precisely to be less vulnerable to variations in student interest. By proposing larger and more generic programs, a sufficient number of students will be guaranteed. A specialization in “radiation science and nuclear technology” will be proposed within several of the master programs. Some of the courses discussed in this paper will be part of this specialization, further increasing the visibility of those courses to Chalmers students.

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